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WP1 – Quality assurance and project management

D1.5 – Ethics Manual

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Authors

Name	Organisation	e-mail	Role
Vasiliki Katsiki	Hypertech	v.katsiki@hypertech.gr	Leading author
Anastasia Chintiadou	Hypertech	a.chintiadou@hypertech.gr	Leading author
Paul Tobin	GECO	paul.tobin@geco-global.com	Contributor
Paschalis Gkaidatzis	CERTH	pgkaidat@iti.gr	Contributor
Dimosthenis Ioannidis	CERTH	djoannid@iti.gr	Contributor
Breffni Lennon	UCC	blennon@ucc.ie	Contributor
Niall P. Dunphy	UCC	n.dunphy@ucc.ie	Contributor
Alexandros Vavouris	Mytilineos	alexandros.vavouris@mytilineos.gr	Contributor
Arjen Schamhart	ESR	Arjen.Schamhart@energiesamenrivierenland.nl	Contributor
Pablo Barrachina	MIWenergia	pablo.barrachina@miwenergia.com	Contributor
Daniele Farrace	AEM	dfarrace@aemsa.ch	Contributor

Reviewers

Name	Organisation	e-mail
Bonnie Murphy	GECO	Bonnie.murphy@geco-global.com
Agnieszka Haider	GECO	agnieszka.haider@geco-global.com
Alessandra Cuneo	RINA-C	alessandra.cuneo@rina.org

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Project Consortium

Austria

- European Center for Renewable Energy Güssing GmbH

Cyprus

- Witside International Markets LTD

Denmark

- Geco Global APS

Greece

- **Hypertech** (Project Coordinator)
- Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis
- Mytilinaios Anonimi Etaireia
- QUE Technologies Kefalaiiouchiki Etaireia

Ireland

- University College Cork
National University of Ireland, Cork

Italy

- Rina Consulting SPA

Netherlands

- Bedrijfsbureau Energie Samen BV
- Cooperatief Energie Dienstenbedrijfs Rivierenland BA

Spain

- My Energia Oner SL
- La Solar Energia Sociedad Cooperativa
- Fundacion Undacion Circe Centre De Investigacion de Recursos Y Consumos Energeticos
- Viesgo Distribucion Electrica SL

Switzerland

- Azienda Elettrica Di Massagno SA

Executive Summary

ACCEPT extends to multiple different geographical and social contexts around Europe, including 4 countries and hundreds of directly involved pilot users. To this end, it is highly important to incorporate ethical aspects in all stages of the research, such as design, development and validation. Confronting these matters at an initial project phase through the definition of a concrete ethics and data management framework will enable the development of innovative technologies while adhering to RRI principles.

A multitude of aspects that are adjacent to ethics revolve are analysed in the document, such as data collection, data protection, transparency and privacy. In parallel the national regulatory framework around data management and pilot participant information requirements are laid out. The processes regarding the ACCEPT living lab set-up are described and an initial preview of the cybersecurity provisions is presented.

All ethical aspects involved in the community engagement will be followed, including prosumer recruitment with **transparency** and a strict **non-discrimination** policy as well as data treatment with the utmost confidentiality. The **right to information** will be respected as the pilot responsible partners are in charge of analysing the ACCEPT concept to the local stakeholders in the local language and using layman language in order ensure proper understanding. A signed consent form hardcopy will confirm the voluntary participation and acknowledgement of each pilot user.

The principles of **data minimisation** will hedge the risk of non-essential data collection and of accidental exposure of personal data (shadow data). Special attention will be paid to the **anonymisation/ pseudonymisation** procedures and to an elaborate user management through the proper **authentication, authorisation** and **encryption** to guarantee secure access to data.

Finally, the deliverable presents the ACCEPT **gender equity plan** covering both the consortium but also the living lab participants. The equity plan will be further enriched through the course of the project.

Table of Contents

Authors	2
Project Consortium	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	7
1.1. <i>Scope and Objectives of task</i>	7
1.2. <i>Structure of deliverable</i>	7
1.3. <i>Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables</i>	8
1.4. <i>Table of abbreviations</i>	9
2. ACCEPT Project Provisions on Ethics Management	10
2.1. <i>Guidelines of Grant Agreement</i>	10
2.2. <i>Ethics Monitoring within the Consortium</i>	15
3. ACCEPT Ethics Management Methodology	18
3.1. <i>Requirements and Methodology</i>	18
3.1.1. Data creation	21
3.1.2. Data collection	21
3.1.3. Data storage	22
3.1.4. Data destruction	23
3.2. <i>Ethical issues relevant to the project</i>	23
3.2.1. Project tasks with ethics requirements	23
3.2.2. ACCEPT Living Labs & Engagement Methodology	25
3.2.3. Cybersecurity framework for data protection & privacy.....	28
3.3. <i>EU & National Legislation on data protection</i>	30
3.3.1. Greek pilot site	31
3.3.2. Dutch pilot site	32
3.3.3. Swiss pilot site	33
3.3.4. Spanish Pilot site.....	34
4. Gender Equity Plan	36
5. Conclusions	38
6. References	39
Annex 1	40
Annex 2	44

Table of Figures

Figure 1 ACCEPT Work Package interdependency schematic.	8
Figure 2 ACCEPT Tasks and Work Packages that elaborate on ethics requirements and management.	9
Figure 3 Data that need to be eliminated from encrypted GDPR-compliant data set	12
Figure 4 Quote on data collection policy recommendation from the Council of Europe	13
Figure 5 Data collection and preservation design principles	14
Figure 6 ACCEPT pilot sites and pre-validation testbeds: location and resources	15
Figure 7 Executive Management Team (EMT) & Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) structure.....	16
Figure 8 Pilot Site Responsible and Involved Partners	17
Figure 9 Pillars of RRI framework	18
Figure 10 Brief preview of data management principles	20
Figure 11 Critical factors considered in data retention	21
Figure 12 Principles of data collection in ACCEPT project	22
Figure 13 The CIA triad	29
Figure 14 Homomorphic Encryption	30
Figure 15 Domains in which ACCEPT attempts to achieve gender balance	36

Table of Tables

Table 1 Deliverables that are related to ethical analysis and management.....	10
Table 2 Task and activities related to sensitive information and areas where ethics apply	23
Table 3 Ethical Self-Evaluation of Living Labs engagements for ACCEPT	26

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of task

Data and Ethics management constitute important pillars of Work Package 1 aiming to analyse all GDPR-related provisions and apply the essential methodologies for adherence to the data protection principles. More specifically, task 1.3 focuses on the implementation of the Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) framework as well as the meticulous monitoring of all the applicable ethical and legal issues in ACCEPT research activities. The objective of the task is to ensure that the proper scrutiny is employed in the handling of personal information of the project members, pilot users and stakeholders in order to avoid infringement of citizen rights.

As a first step in the procedure of the data and ethics management, a set of guidelines is stipulated as benchmarks for monitoring throughout the project duration. These guidelines/ requirements are defined on the basis of national and European regulation and further to the ACCEPT Grant Agreement provisions. The ethics manual (D1.5) and the data management plan (D1.2) actually contain the roadmap and the elaborations on managing ethical issues pertaining to data collection, citizen data privacy, etc. More particularly, the data management plan (DMP) includes the Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) according to the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) while the ethics manual focuses horizontally on the legal and ethical issues that may appear through the course of the project.

ACCEPT project will engage hundreds of end-users in many geographical and social contexts in four European countries during the design, development but mostly the validation phase. That is why privacy and protection of sensitive data are considered important aspects and as analysed with such thoroughness in WP1. Addressing these issues at an early stage will facilitate the development of innovative technologies and solutions enabling smart and renewable-based local energy communities, e.g. blockchain-enabled flexibility markets, etc.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

The present report attempts to specify and document all applicable ethical and legal issues related to the project activities and pilots, which derive from EU/national regulations and policies around data privacy. The objective of the deliverable is to formulate the process of scrutiny that is required in order to hedge and confront any potential infringements on citizens' privacy from ACCEPT research activities. The guidelines set from the Grant Agreement are summarised and the internal governance bodies that are assigned with ethics monitoring are presented. Moreover, the methodology of ethical management in the project living labs, in the data collection procedure, in the ex-ante pilot surveys and in the post-collection data handling are detailed along with contextual information from the EU and national data protection regulations. Last but not least, in the frame of ethics management the Gender Equity Plan of the project is also outlined given that gender balance and proper representation is a major requirement in the ACCEPT framework.

As mentioned above, WP1 thoroughly investigates the ethics management and the proper consideration of all applicable GDPR and RRI-related provisions into ACCEPT research framework. A very brief reference has been made in Quality Assurance Handbook (D1.1). An extensive analysis is following in the present document and in the data management plan (DMP). These two deliverables (D1.2 & D1.5) constitute together an important milestone (MS3) as per the ACCEPT Grant Agreement [1]. While the Data Management Plan (DMP) will be enriched through multiple versions within the project (three

versions overall – D1.2, D1.3, D1.4), the ethics manual will be followed by a conclusion report at the end of the project, namely D1.6 “RRI reporting and Ethics Management Report”, summarizing the social impact of it and documenting that no “disruption” has been caused through the pilot activities.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

As described above, task 1.3 is extended throughout the span of the project and is linked to all the research and pilot activities. They should be considered as an input in all work packages and tasks especially the ones that are related with solution deployment, pilot site ex-ante surveys, validation activities and community engagement. Besides forming input requirements, task 1.3 also examines those methodologies followed in the above-mentioned activities in WP2-6-7-8 ensure compliance with the ethical framework and the applicable data protection regulations. Figure 1 presents schematically the interdependencies between the different WPs of ACCEPT and the role of WP1 relative to the project elaborations.

Figure 1 ACCEPT Work Package interdependency schematic.

Besides the indirect interdependencies with other tasks and work packages of the ACCEPT project, different aspects of ethics are elaborated in many deliverables of the project, as shown in Figure 2. While WP11 focuses on the ethics requirements related to humans that are participating in the project, T1.1 covers the internal management bodies in charge of the ethics monitoring, T1.3 includes a more elaborate approach on the RRI and GDPR provisions and T2.4 presents a more applied approach of the Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design.

Figure 2 ACCEPT Tasks and Work Packages that elaborate on ethics requirements and management.

1.4. Table of abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EAB	Ethics Advisory Board
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equity
ePD	ePrivacy Directive
EGE	European Group on Ethics
EMT	Executive Management Team
FADP	Federal Act on Data Protection
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H	Humans
IMP	Innovation Management Plan
LEPPI	Legal Ethical Privacy and Policy Issues
LL	Living Lab
MS	Milestone
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
PC	Project Coordinator
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
SC	Steering Committee
SEAC	Security Access Control
TM	Technical Manager
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

2. ACCEPT Project Provisions on Ethics Management

2.1. Guidelines of Grant Agreement

Due respect to the ethical aspects of research and compliance with national, regional and EU legislation and ethics directives are of utmost importance for ACCEPT project. The majority of aspects that are adjacent to ethics provisions revolve around data collection, data protection, privacy, transparency with regards to the information provided to involved stakeholders in order for them to make informed decisions. To this end, from the Grant Agreement phase of the project the guidelines in terms of policy, ethical and privacy procedures had been laid out. More specifically, the aforementioned procedures include:

- a. managerial resolution of ethical issues within the consortium;
- b. user engagement and proper access to information;
- c. data collection and protection;
- d. discrete nomination of a declared Legal-Ethical-Privacy and Policy Issues (LEPPI) advisor within the consortium coordinating any potential arising LEPPI.

Annex 1 [1] specifically dedicates a series of deliverables to define ethical requirements both regarding humans participating in the research and data handling, to monitor the ethical management and establish consortium procedures around the topic. A brief presentation of the deliverables that are related to ethical analysis and management is included in Table 1 together with a short description of their specific relevance.

Table 1 Deliverables that are related to ethical analysis and management

Deliverable No	Content Description	Relevance
D1.1/ D1.7/ D1.8	Project Management Handbook & Quality Assurance Plan v1/v2/v3	Analysis and inclusion of ethical aspects in the management of the project, e.g., ethical risk identification, governance bodies of the project, etc.
D1.2/ D1.3/ D1.4	Data Management Plan v1/v2/v3	Description of data protection provisions and of the manner that the ethical aspects -such as transparency, privacy, pseudonymisation etc.- have been integrated in ACCEPT data management.
D1.5	Ethics Manual	The overall ethics requirements and management strategy within ACCEPT project.
D1.6	RRI reporting & Ethics Management Report	Analysis of “Responsible Research and Innovation” principles incorporating ethical aspects, e.g. research integrity, science & society correlation, etc.
D2.5/ D2.6	Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection and privacy v1/v2	It presents the security access and data protection framework that is applied in the data management and interoperability platform of ACCEPT.
D3.1/ D3.2/ D3.3/ D3.4	Living Lab activities plan and evaluation report v1/v2/v3/v4	It outlines how the recruitment and living lab methodologies incorporate data protection, non-discrimination and transparency principles.

D11.1	H-Requirement No. 1	It focuses on the requirements on research participants in ACCEPT research.
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Ethics-related issues are divided into two (2) categories:

- **“Humans” (H)** referring to the processes and requirements that are utilized for participant recruitment in the research framework.
- **Protection of Personal Data (POPD)** analysing the procedures of information Collection – Storage – Protection – Retrieval -Destruction and verification of compliance with application data regulation.

The first category refers to the pilot site stakeholders that will voluntarily join the demonstration activities of ACCEPT framework in its four (4) pilot sites in Greece, Spain, Switzerland and Holland, as specified in WP7. The manner that the pilot users will be approached and recruited by the ACCEPT consortium shall be in accordance with the Article 43 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [2]. Indicatively, GDPR defines as personal information any data that can be used to detect a person both directly and indirectly. Such data include pictures, names/ surnames, ID information, addresses, social media accounts or electronic detection data such as e-mails, IPs, etc. Such information when it refers to a specific “Data Subject” [2] is considered sensitive and requires the determination of specific processing rules.

To this end, after the specification of the technical criteria that are essential for the pilot users in order to be part of ACCEPT research activities, specific requirements, processes and structures need to be created and applied in order to ensure that the user personal information will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. More specifically, confidentiality will be ensured if the personal data of the research participants are not present in any deliverable report. Furthermore, besides refraining from revealing the data, it should also be ensured that an indirect connection to the user cannot be made through combination of revealed data. Therefore, pseudonymisation that is irreversible shall be ensured as well as a concrete post-project data destruction shall be defined. According to ACCEPT Grant Agreement, the encrypted personal information shall not include or be linked to the data of Figure 3.

Figure 3 Data that need to be eliminated from encrypted GDPR-compliant data set

The above needs to be taken into account from the early beginning of consumer engagement and community recruitment activities through the ACCEP Living Labs (T3.3/ D3.3). The Living Lab participants shall be recruited with **transparency** reassuring that **no discrimination** is conducted and that their data are treated with the proper confidentiality. Elaboration on the recruitment criteria as well as the essential participant “Informed Consent” and “Project Information Sheet” templates are provided in D11.1 [3] already submitted in M1 of the project. More particularly, the “Project Information Sheet” will be enriched later in the project with more specific information regarding the use cases and demonstration scenarios per pilot site in order for the users to be fully aware of the scope, purpose and objectives of the demos that they contribute to. In other words, no research activity that involves the processing of encrypted data can take place without the legal consent of the physical persons involved and no processing of this type of data will take place unless it is absolutely essential.

According to the DoA, the consent procedure should include two serial milestones:

- The pilot site partner should analyse in detail the research concept of ACCEPT to the stakeholders involved in each pilot together with the expectations from their participation. What is required and expected from each pilot user is linked to the level of potential infringement on their personal data. Through such a procedure, transparency is guaranteed and each potential participant can make an informed decision on whether they should participate or not in the project activities.
- Further to the verbal interaction, a written and signed consent form is essential in order to confirm voluntary participation and acknowledgement of the pilot activity involvement

requirements. Together with the English language, the informed consent also needs to be translated in the local language of the country of the pilot site to ensure proper comprehension of the content. In terms of content, the information sheet should include **description of project scope and objectives**, elicitation and processing of **progress in terms of pilot site deployment and validation activities** as well as a detailed reference on **unrestricted disclaimer rights**.

Proper measurements should be taken in order to prohibit any possibility of second-layer personal data process, e.g. through selling them for use outside the project purposes, etc. Additionally, data minimisation policy should be applied to prevent the collection of information that is not essential. Finally, the project participants should be age-appropriate as well as free and fully aware of the consent that they are providing. The non-discriminatory policy following the Council of Europe's Recommendation will be applied (refer to Figure 4).

“The collection of data on individuals solely on the basis that they have a particular racial origin, particular religious convictions, sexual behaviour or political opinions or belong to particular movements or organisations which are not proscribed by law should be prohibited. The collection of data concerning these factors may only be carried out if absolutely necessary for the purposes of a particular inquiry”

Europe's Recommendation R(87)15, Art.2

Figure 4 Quote on data collection policy recommendation from the Council of Europe

The second ethics-related category actually follows the first one and is related to the exact definition of the data process involving the stages of collection, protection, storage as well as retention and destruction. All these processes have been outlined in the ACCEPT DoA in compliance with the applicable EU legislation. Their application in the project is actually a continuous and dynamic procedure which will be ensured by the Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) and the LEPPi Officer (ref. to paragraph 2.2). Finally, if and when needed the consortium will ask various committees for experts' opinion, such as the European Group on Ethics (EGE).

In terms of technical infrastructure provisions, a fully-fledged Security Access (SEAC) framework is planned to be created in ACCEPT in order to ensure proper user authentication and authorisation prior to accessing the data management platform. In general, all pillars of secure data preservation -namely availability, integrity and confidentiality- will be safeguarded from misuse. The approach will be elaborated in WP2 weighing the impact of ethical risks (ref. to Art.35 [2]). Some of the basic principles that will be followed in the design are included in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Data collection and preservation design principles

The specific provisions on confidentiality data handling covering all stages of storage – collection- end-of-project life destruction will be in compliance with H2020 Online Manual regarding Ethics [4]. Focusing on ACCEPT living lab resources and pilots, Figure 6 summarises the testbeds incorporated in the project. Each of them is assigned to at least one partner that is responsible and acts as a link between the research framework and the local ecosystem, including the data collection framework and the compliance with the local legislation on data protection. In all cases, by principle the personal data are property of its individual with respect to the local regulation.

Pilot Sites	Buildings (Type & No.)
nZEB Smart House (CERTH)	1 residential building (Detached 2-storey house)
VIESGO Testbed	Dataset through electronic platform
Hypertech Lab and Friendly Users	1 commercial (office) and 9 residential buildings
Aspra Spitia Pilot site (Mytilineos)	34 apartments in 12-storey building, 19 fully-electric on-duty flats, 10 fully electric guest houses 63 installations in total
Murcia Pilot site (LaSolar)	50 residential building
Capriasca & Massagno Pilot	35 flats in 11 residential buildings 1 public pool 1 District Heating plant 1 commercial building (4 offices) 1 elderly care home (30 flats)
Eva Lanxmeer Community (EDBR)	50 households 2 parking lots including EV charging and RES generators, central Heat Pump connected to DH network

Figure 6 ACCEPT pilot sites and pre-validation testbeds: location and resources

According to the DoA guidelines, in the incidence of data collection during the ex-ante pilot surveys, the living lab activities and the use-case definition, the proper encryption will be applied through pseudonymisation. More specifically, homomorphic encryption methodology or equivalent is suggested. With the data traceability to their sources being removed for the majority of the participants, only key responsible personnel will hold the encryption “keys”. Such an assignment will be done with the proper formalities and the data destruction will be conducted in due time after the project completion. The exact procedure of data preservation timelines and the further categorisation in data models, metadata, etc. will be conducted in the ACCEPT Data Management Plan (D1.2/ D1.3/ D1.4).

2.2. Ethics Monitoring within the Consortium

As defined in deliverable D1.1 [5], the project governance bodies (GA, SC, etc.) are in charge of the overall management, process control and contingency planning. Apart from the bodies there are also personalised responsibilities with key personnel having the roles of Project Coordinator (PC), Living Lab Manager, etc. The key managing roles of the project form the Executive Management Team (EMT), which is also in charge of ethics monitoring in the frame of ACCEPT quality assurance. Namely it assumes the role of Ethics Advisory Board (EAB). The EAB together with the LEPMI Officer are in charge of

conducting the essential scrutiny in the research procedures in order to ensure that there is no risk of privacy breaching both on the technical and managerial level.

Given that ACCEPT project involves a consortium of many partners that work in parallel in different aspects of the research topic – as described in the project work packages- there is a risk of misinformation. ACCEPT intends to resolve it through a robust and clear procedure that includes the allocation of smaller responsibilities on work package and task level to their respective leaders followed by a regular (monthly) progress monitoring where the responsible partners have the opportunity to report any ethical risk or access security problems to the GA, EAB and PC. The Executive Management Team (EMT) and thus Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) structure is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Executive Management Team (EMT) & Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) structure

The Ethical Advisory Board's (EAB) role is the monitoring and supervision of the pilot surveys, the living labs and the validation activities behind the ACCEPT results concerning their ethical aspects. On the other hand, the LEPEI officer, which is Dr. Dimosthenis Ioannidis from CERTH for ACCEPT project, is in charge of overseeing the ethical aspects particularly involved in certain technical activities, trials, data management and data processing.

As dictated by the GA, all the beneficiaries are expected to submit to the PC and EAB any opinions and notifications related to ethical issues immediately when these come to their attention. Especially the beneficiaries that are involved in the project pilots have an advanced supervisory role with respect to the information management related to the end-user and stakeholder engagement, the privacy of which should be safeguarded through anonymisation techniques. A horizontal and important role on the issue also burdens the ACCEPT Living Lab Manager. All provisions of the EU directives, the Grant Agreement

and the national bodies should be applied. Figure 8 present the responsible partners per pilot site for both validation and pre-validation activities.

Beyond the allocated duties to single partners, it holds that the overall ACCEPT consortium is attentive to safeguard the research participants’ personal data which are considered of ultimate. To this end, compliance with legal and ethical guidelines is ensured and the essential measures are taken into account during the project activities. Ethical, legal and privacy issues already are and will continue to be in the agendas of the consortium meeting and reporting procedures.

Figure 8 Pilot Site Responsible and Involved Partners

3. ACCEPT Ethics Management Methodology

3.1. Requirements and Methodology

Respect to the free will and non-discriminatory engagement of the research participants is one pillar of the ACCEPT ethics framework which is extensively analysed in D11.1 [3]. The other pillar is the handling of personal data. By default, the term “personal data” is used to identify any piece of information that is directly or indirectly linked to a physical person [6]. These personal data include the names, contact details, affiliations, etc.

The ACCEPT project partners are well aware of the ethical implications in their research framework as well as the ethical guidelines and rules that need to be respected in the frame of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). The RRI principles include all societal issues that are involved in research and the impact of the latter on society. These include several ethical aspects, such as safeguarding research integrity, open access to research finding while safeguarding sensitive information of the research subjects, promoting gender equality and balance, etc. The RRI principles will be analysed later in the project and will be reported in D1.6. The mention herein is just introductory in order to indicate the orientation of ACCEPT consortium with regards to its Ethics Management methodology. The schematic of Figure 9 summarises the pillars of RRI framework.

Figure 9 Pillars of RRI framework

The ACCEPT specific ethics management methodology will be laid out starting from a set of rules that are applied in the project processes and elaboration. These are listed as follows:

- ❖ Elaborated check for full compliance with all applicable regulations -both on EU and national levels- for ethical issues.
- ❖ Meticulous and iterative check of possible violations of privacy rights of the research participants in terms of data handling.
- ❖ Submission, if and where necessary, of a declaration of compliance with respect to the privacy legislation of each pilot country. This may be applicable with respect to WP6 activities starting from T6.1 “Ex-Ante pilot surveys”.
- ❖ The Informed Consent templates will be translated in the language of the data subjects that it addresses and will be stored in the project common repository. A initial template that will be the basis for the translation and further elaboration is already provided in the GA and the D11.1 [3].
- ❖ The drafting and signing of informed consents will be conducted before the start of the corresponding tasks the activities of which are related to it.
- ❖ The methodology followed in the Living Lab organisation and operation will take into account the applicable ethical aspects. A specific description will be provided in the deliverables of T3.1 “ACCEPT Living Labs design & establishment” but also in the present deliverable in paragraph 3.2.2.
- ❖ The procedure of signed consent forms signing is highly relative to the community recruitment and therefore it will be conducted in the frame of WP3 and T6.1.
- ❖ A specific investigation will be conducted on whether there is a need to appoint a Data Protection Officer (DPO) or not. If according to the GDPR provisions there is no need for a DPO, a thorough protection policy on data should be submitted in the frame of WP1 deliverables.
- ❖ Data management is a cornerstone for ethics management and to this end a specific mention is made herein and an elaborate analysis in deliverables D1.2, D1.3 and D1.4.
- ❖ Based on the definition of ACCEPT data model -to be conducted in the system architecture task of the project- a detailed justification of the data processing will follow in the cybersecurity framework design deliverable. This document together with the data management deliverable should describe all the essential steps to be followed for the safeguarding of the data subjects’ rights, including pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation to be applied in the data management process.
- ❖ During all stages of data collection and processing, the stakeholders will be fully aware of the handling details.
- ❖ The best data management platforms in the fields of energy demand and consumer profiling will be followed and applied in the project. Further insights on that topic will be provided in the Data Management Plan (DMP), which will be processed as a living document through the project lifetime in order to be enriched in each iteration with new insights, best practices incorporated through experts’ opinion or consultation of third-party ethics bodies, etc. Through the multiple iterations of the task, any impediments encountered or new regulatory aspects introduced can be taken into account and can be properly documented.
- ❖ Full compliance with the legislative frameworks is ensured on both international and national level, including the following provisions:
 - Fully informing all research participants of prior to requesting their consent to data retrieval and processing.
 - Participation is voluntary and the users have the right to withdraw at any stage of the research.
 - The signing of the informed consent forms confirms the consensus of the user in terms of their involvement in the project activities.

- Under no circumstances does any member of the consortium with access to the data have the right to sell the information collected with the project for commercial or any other purposes.
- Central data storage will be avoided, if possible.
- The overall approach of the project is data minimisation according to which all the tasks and surveys will strictly request information that is essential and will strictly collect the minimum data sets required to cover the project needs.
- By principle, there will be immediate destruction of any potential data shadows created by the user participation in online activities, etc.
- As mentioned above, the data sets will not be used for racial, religious, political and gender or sexual profiling of the users and a strict non-discriminatory policy will be applied in compliance with the EU legislative guidelines.

Figure 10 Brief preview of data management principles

Figure 10 summarises some key principles to be further detailed in the ACCEPT Data Management Plan (DMP). One additional issue that will also be addressed there is the **accidental disclosure of information that is indirectly linked to a data subject**. In terms of creating unidentifiable data sets the following parameters must be taken into account:

- a. No personal names or details will be included in the project deliverables. Only statistics, or derivative findings and conclusions can appear in the reports.
- b. The data will be pseudonymised -if not able to be completely anonymized- in a way that no permanent link can be established between the real and the processed personal data.
- c. The correspondence with the real and the pseudonymised data will be stored in a different server that has proper security access specifications.
- d. In cases that there is not a possibility to provide confidentiality, such as face-2-face meetings, living lab workshops, stakeholder discussions, etc, there will be a very careful handling of the personal data. As an example, photos of events that include the research participants' images will not be able to be disseminated unless the users are properly informed of the intended use of the dissemination material and they provide their consent to the usage of the footage.

In case there is a scientific need for data retention in terms of open research purposes, then a set of parameters, which are presented in Figure 11, need to be considered and the proper justification needs to be prepared in order to support the argument of data retention.

Figure 11 Critical factors considered in data retention

3.1.1. Data creation

Given the involvement of surveys and the establishment of wide living labs, the process of “data creation” is part of the project. According to the legislation terminology, the process of data creation does not only refer to brand new data but also to an existing one that is new for the specific scope of interest.

According to this approach, the partners that are responsible for the “data creation”, namely the storage, processing and distribution of a gathered set of information, are also in charge of the anonymisation/ pseudonymisation and the cleansing of the data set from sensitive/ personal details. In the case of another member of the consortium wanting to process an already created data set for another use, they become in charge of determining the data source and of the privacy assessment.

3.1.2. Data collection

Based on the methodological approach analysed herein and the guidelines of the national and regional data protection regulations, the data collection procedure within ACCEPT will follow a set of rules and principles as presented in Figure 12.

The bottom-line of all the measures is that the personal information will be treated as confidential and according to the applicable directive of data privacy and security. All the stakeholders of the ACCEPT framework are not only allowed but also welcomed to edit, revise and raise questions during the project Living Lab activities.

Figure 12 Principles of data collection in ACCEPT project

3.1.3. Data storage

The part of data storage is covered in paragraph 3.1.3. The principles include safe storage and controlled, secure access to data which is enabled through anonymisation/ pseudonymisation and user authentication, authorisation, encryption procedure. The use of open-source tools in order to create the appropriate authorisation and encryption framework is advised but it will be defined in the frame of T2.4. Technical data storage guidelines further include:

- Infiltration protection
- Access Control measures
- Physical protection of core storage infrastructure

3.1.4. Data destruction

Given that digital infrastructure is utilised for data storage, the indicated methodologies for permanent and irreversible data destruction should be followed. These could be hard drive overwriting and re-formatting tools, etc. The data destruction timeline is fixed at one (1) after the completion of the project but a sole exception of public models and their corresponding datasets that could be maintained if they have some justified use for purposes of project exploitation, etc.

3.2. Ethical issues relevant to the project

3.2.1. Project tasks with ethics requirements

Table 1 in paragraph 2.1 summarises all the deliverables that are related to ethical analysis and management. In the present paragraph, a summary is presented in Table 2 of the task that require intensive ethics monitoring given the nature of their activities that either involve the active user participation or the processing of their personal data.

The analysis is based on a thorough review of the work structure, work package and task scopes and objectives in combination with the pillars of ethics management.

Table 2 Task and activities related to sensitive information and areas where ethics apply

Task No. & Descriptions		Description of ethical aspects involved
WP2	Foundations	
T2.1	Market actor & prosumer requirements & business case definition	For the use case and requirements definitions, surveys may be distributed to stakeholders and pilot participants. Attention should be paid to shadow data or publishing on contact details, etc.
T2.4	Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers	The design should include all applicable aspects for proper data protection -namely anonymisation & pseudonymisation- but also an appropriate user management strategy that safeguards the access to stored data with authentication- authorisation and encryption techniques.
T2.5	Preliminary design of business models for compound services and associated SLAs/contracts	Same cross-cutting issues with T2.1
WP3	Energy governance, communities and demonstration site analysis	
T3.1	ACCEPT Living Labs design & establishment	During the stakeholder engagement processes such as personal contact exchange, face-to-face meetings and in general collection of information in order to conduct the essential profiling for the creation of a human-centric digital framework. All these processes need to be monitored in order to be in compliance with local and EU legislation as well as with RRI principles.

T3.4	Stakeholder and community mapping at pilot sites	Same cross-cutting issues with T3.1
WP6	ACCEPT solution integration, pre-validation, roll-out	
T6.1	Ex-ante pilot site surveys	When it comes to a Demand Response and Energy Community framework, in order to map the resources on ex-ante basis there is a need to conduct surveys on building-level and gather information on domestic appliances, energy consumption, etc. This requires fully informing the property owners concerning the scope, targets and data needs of the pilot set-up.
T6.4	Pre-validation of ACCEPT solution in controlled environments	The application of the solution for pre-validation requires data processing and use of ACCEPT data storage and management platform that needs to have the Security Access framework and be in compliance with data privacy measures.
T6.5	Pilot site preparation and demonstration/validation scenario definition	Same cross-cutting issues with T6.1
T6.6	ACCEPT solution deployment, roll-out & beta-testing at pilot premises	Same cross-cutting issues with T6.1
WP7	ACCEPT demonstration & validation activities	
T7.1	Consumer validation of service and content design	In combination with the aspects described in T6.4, the results from the validation activities need to be combined with further socio-economic aspects that may be retrieved from surveys, etc. Special attention needs to be paid in order to ensure non-discriminatory, transparent use of data with confidentiality.
T7.2	Demonstration at the Murcia (ES) pilot site	Same cross-cutting issues with T6.4
T7.3	Demonstration at the Aspra Spitia (GR) pilot site	Same cross-cutting issues with T6.4
T7.4	Demonstration at the Massagno (CH) pilot site	Same cross-cutting issues with T6.4
T7.5	Demonstration at the Culemborg (NL) pilot site	Same cross-cutting issues with T6.4
WP8	Impact assessment & business modelling	
T8.1	Analysis of innovation obstacles for energy communities and demand response	Same cross-cutting issues with T7.1
T8.3	Impact assessment of demonstrated solutions	Same cross-cutting issues with T6.4 & T7.1

T8.4	Synthesis of consumer centric compound DR design	Same cross-cutting issues with T7.1
WP9	Outreach activities for impact enhancement	
T9.2	Dissemination and communication activities	Many times, in dissemination and communication activities, photographs or other material retrieved from physical meetings and events is published on social media or other channels. There is a need to make sure that all persons that are included in this material have provided their consent to do so and are aware of where this material will be published.

3.2.2. ACCEPT Living Labs & Engagement Methodology

The ACCEPT project utilises a user-driven innovation and engagement through the ACCEPT living labs to provide a platform for experience sharing and knowledge exchange, working with real users on outcome validation and user- and business-driven open innovation. Consequently, the ACCEPT living lab activities are oriented towards fulfilling the following objectives:

- Widely disseminate the project outcomes towards end-users, beneficiaries and energy stakeholders so as to generate a broad awareness and engagement/ involvement in the various project activities;
- Create opportunities for further exploitation and replication of the project results after completion;
- Obtain feedback from major stakeholders, end-users and targeted beneficiaries throughout project duration to optimize all project developments, so as to directly address critical needs of stakeholders involved in the operation of the ACCEPT framework.
- Support knowledge and experience sharing with international partners together with other selected stakeholders from the country.

To achieve these objectives, the ethical considerations of working with human stakeholders in a collaborative environment have been assessed in detail. Engagement activities in WP3 comprise mainly interviews and surveys and will mostly take place in WP3. The ACCEPT consortium will comply with all relevant national, European and international ethical regulations and professional codes of conduct and will conform to Horizon 2020 ethical guidelines. These include the Data Protection Directive (95/46/EC), the European Commission’s “Data Protection and Privacy Ethics Guidelines” and its “Guidance for Applicants on Informed Consent”, along with corresponding national regulations.

Engagement activities within ACCEPT operate under the guidance of the ‘do no harm’ principle, which sees researchers ensure that the consequences of their decisions and actions do not harm respondents. The overall project leader and work package leaders, and all supporting partners work in compliance with the scientific and ethical standards in their home country, incorporating best practice principles including:

- **Transparency** regarding all data collection and management practices performed by the project, including making all participants and stakeholders aware of the processes involved;

- Communicate (both verbally and written) with participants in participating CECs **using Informed Consent**, with participants made aware of the option to withdraw from the project at any time;
- A **robust data protection program**, whereby all security and privacy issues are integrated into the projects overall security and ethics management policy.

All empirical data collected will be anonymised/ pseudonymised, with participants’ names and other identifying indicators coded. A complete ethics self-assessment (see Table 3 below) of all planned living lab activities has been carried out in order for the project to be compliant with the appropriate national, EU, and international laws.

Table 3 Ethical Self-Evaluation of Living Labs engagements for ACCEPT

1	Is it considered that the project has significant ethical implications?	No
2	Will the objectives, and the methods used, for the living lab engagements be described to participants in advance, so that they are informed about what to expect?	Yes
3	Will participation be voluntary?	Yes
4	Will written informed consent be obtained from participants?	Yes
5	Will participants be told they may withdraw from the research at any time and for any reason?	Yes
6	Will data be treated with full confidentiality / anonymity (as appropriate)?	Yes
7	Will data be securely held for a minimum period of ten years after the completion of a research project?	Yes
8	If results are published, will anonymity be maintained, and participants not identified?	Yes
9	In the event that data from the living labs is shared between consortium partners, will anonymity be maintained?	Yes
10	Will participants be debriefed at the end of their participation	Yes
11	Will the project involve deliberately misleading participants in any way?	No
12	Will participants include children and/or young persons under 18 years of age?	No
13	Will participants include people with learning or communication difficulties?	No
14	Will participants include people in custody?	No
15	Will participants include people engaged in illegal activities (<i>e.g.</i> drug taking, violent acts <i>etc.</i>)	No
16	Is there a realistic risk of participants experiencing any physical or psychological distress?	No
17	Will living labs participants receive payment / gifts / voucher / <i>etc.</i> for participating	No

The two key areas of concern arising from this type of work which require ethical consideration have been identified. They comprise the issues of “Protection of Personal data” and interacting with “Humans”. Consequently, a programme of procedures is being adopted that guarantees the data protection of participating citizens and energy consumers. Any information managed by the project consortium during its **living labs activities may be of a private or confidential nature**. Therefore, all information/data gathered will be carefully controlled, both during collection (*e.g.* the living labs engagements, events *etc.*) and later when this data is being later stored and analysed, with appropriate restriction policies in place.

Below is a detailed description of how the community engagement activities for ACCEPT will be done with regard to working with people and the collection and processing of their personal data. In particular, it will focus on:

- 1.) the procedures to be carried out that will inform and engage with citizens and consumers, and guarantee their rights,
- 2.) how that data is collected, processed and protected.

A standard approach to data collection ethics has been adopted since the start of the project, since ACCEPT does involve working with human participants and personal data collection and processing.

Working with Humans

For all interviews and surveys, ACCEPT is already implementing procedures for data protection that comply with EU and national regulations in all involved countries. Having considered the nature of the work involved and informed by the ethical self-assessment summarised above, the following guiding principles are being applied to all human engagement activities planned for ACCEPT. They include:

- Voluntary participation: participation is entirely voluntary, and this will be made explicitly clear to all potential participants.
- Informed Consent: informed consent from participants will be sought before collecting and storing any collected material in paper or electronic form. Before being invited to give written consent to participate, participants will be informed of the nature of the project, the purpose of their engagement in the project, how their data will be used, how it will be controlled, stored and ultimately disposed of.
- Adult participants: participants will be asked to confirm they are over the age of 18 before being allowed to participate.
- Right to withdraw: participants have the right to withdraw from the living labs activities at any time. This will be made explicitly clear to them in the initial briefing document. Where data can be linked to a specific participant (*e.g.*, audio or video recordings), participants can withdraw consent at any time during and up to two weeks after the collection of the data. Any associated transcripts or other written material will only refer to the coded name assigned to that participant. Where data has been gathered anonymously participants may withdraw up until submission of the data.
- Storage of information: When the data collection is completed, data will be anonymised at the earliest possible point in time.
- Security will include:
 - **encryption of laptops (*e.g.*, using Filevault on OSX, Bitlocker on Windows);**
 - **password protection on all audio and/or video recordings;**
 - **prohibition on the use of USB memory keys for all such research data;**
 - **use of secure network file storage in preference to cloud-based solutions**

- Data sharing among partners: any data obtained by one partner in the ACCEPT consortium will always be anonymised before sharing with other partners. In addition, data sharing will require data sharing agreements between those partners.

Data Management

Data management for ACCEPT living lab activities will be subject to ethical approval, institutional codes of research conduct; funding agency requirements, and regulatory obligations. All data will be collected in accordance with EU legislation (GDPR) and all relevant national data regulations. The data from the living labs will also be managed by the task leader in keeping with the FAIR data standards of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. The following procedures will be adhered in order to protect the personal data of participants:

- All collected data will remain with the organisation that collects it;
- The collected data will be kept on secure servers;
- Anonymisation/ Pseudonymisation procedures will be implemented to protect data confidentiality;
- All raw data will not be shared. However, anonymised results may be shared between work package partners where appropriate.

All reporting on living labs activities will see the anonymity of participants fully guaranteed. Most notably, this will involve anonymising direct quotations, descriptions, *etc.* No direct identifiers (*e.g.* names, email addresses, *etc.*) or other information that would enable a person to deduce the identity of a participant will be used in any of our reports. Where total anonymity is not possible, the consent of those involved will be sought before publication. In the event that any collected information is accidentally identifiable it will be neither sensitive nor potentially damaging. Any text produced based on research results from the living labs will respect this principle of privacy and anonymity. Participants will not be identifiable, unless they are representing a view of their organization and only then with their prior personal and written consent.

Data Protection

The project partners responsible for collecting and processing all potentially personal data during the living labs activities either already have a Data Protection Officer (DPO) appointed under the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) or will appoint an appropriate person to serve an equivalent role specifically for this project. Contact details of the DPO of the relevant organisation(s) will be made available to all participants during the project.

3.2.3. Cybersecurity framework for data protection & privacy

This section includes the description of the potential security hazards that may be present in the context of the ACCEPT system, as well as the protection mechanisms that will be implemented in order to address the risks that are posed.

Since the collected data can be found both stored and exchanged over the network, the security design contains mechanisms that aim to protect these two different forms of data. Namely, the Data-at-Rest and the Data-in-Transit. Every Security design should focus on the preservation of Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability principles, also known as the CIA triad, Figure 13. More specifically:

- **Confidentiality** concerns the preservation of unauthorized access to data. Measures that are considered to address such problems include secure authentication mechanisms as well as data encryption, both for data at rest and data in transit.

- **Integrity** focuses on the prevention data corruption. In other words, data should always remain complete and accurate. The countermeasures that are considered for such purposes, are techniques that mark the data with a checksum that act as a verifier of the data integrity. Additionally, the capability of data modification should be limited only to authorized users and only if the data are inside their field of interest.
- **Availability** describes the capability of authorized users to gain access to the data at all times. The access to data can be hindered, by targeting a system’s availability first. Techniques that act as countermeasures may involve Network Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems, so as to ensure that a system stays unaffected of such attacks.

Figure 13 The CIA triad

The CIA triad described above contributes to the detection of the threats taken into consideration, which then lead to the choice of the security mechanisms that need to be implemented. These threats can be classified into the following categories:

- **Eavesdropping:** Such attacks refer to the capturing of the network flow packets in order to obtain access to the information exchanged, by unauthorized users.
- **Unauthorized access to system resources:** This kind of attacks include both malicious users that aim to penetrate the system, as well as insiders that may not be authorized to access a certain type of data/resource. This may lead to stored data breach intentionally or not.
- **Denial of service:** A denial of Service (DoS) attack targets a system’s availability, by orchestrating a network flooding attack, namely sending numerous of network packets that leads to exhaustion of the resources.
- **Man in the Middle:** A man-in-the-middle (MITM) involves intercepting trusted communications by malicious users, with the purpose of either stealing information exchanged, and even altering it.

All of the above threats can ultimately lead to data breach, and in certain cases even in system compromise.

In order to mitigate the aforementioned threats, several security mechanisms are planned to be implemented. First of all, a strong authentication mechanism that ensures that only authorized users have access to the systems resources and data, is going to be designed. Especially, Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) is planned to be designed, in order to build a robust control against unauthorized use.

The second level of protection concerns the data that are stored in the databases. No information should remain unencrypted. Hence, encryption algorithms for the Data-at-Rest will be implemented with a

focus on the balance between the data protection from malicious users and the data availability to authorized ones. Moreover, encryption keys protection and management are taken into consideration, as they can be the single point of failure to the whole Data-at-Rest encryption design. In order to make the information stored, more secured, homomorphic encryption algorithms are going to be researched. Homomorphic encryption enables users to perform calculations on encrypted data, without decryption required. A depiction of this technique is presented in Figure 14. This will reduce the risk of data breaches, as less users should have access to plaintext information and thus, encryption/decryption keys.

Figure 14 Homomorphic Encryption

Data should also be protected while they are in transit. Securing the communication channels, involves the implementation of encryption algorithms, dedicated for network communication. Communication encryption algorithms can be categorized as shown, according to the type of key(s) they involve:

- Symmetric algorithms require a single key for both encryption and decryption purposes
- Asymmetric algorithms require a public key for encryption purposes, and a different private key for decryption

An asymmetric encryption algorithm will be implemented to ensure the confidentiality of exchanged data, as they are more secure in comparison with symmetric ones.

Finally, special consideration is taken to remove the traceability of information, while maintaining the required information intact. While possible, anonymisation techniques, will be applied. Namely, the data collected will be cleaned from any type of information that can act as an indicator of a data subject. However, in case complete anonymisation cannot be applied, a pseudonymization scheme will be implemented. During this process the data subject identifiers are not removed, however they are replaced with pseudonyms. The pairing of the subjects and the corresponding pseudonyms is stored in a secure database, encrypted.

3.3. EU & National Legislation on data protection

The ACCEPT project partners are fully aware of the ethical aspects implied in the research and are willing to respect all applicable ethical rules and HORIZON RRI standards as well as the ones that are included Fundamental Rights Chapter of the EU.

The project activities will have the most ethical, privacy and data protection implications are obviously linked to the four pilots in Greece, Netherlands, Switzerland and Spain that will include a wide data collection from residential and commercial assets in order to assess the overall impact of the developed framework. As expected, a large number of human participants will be involved in multiple activities of the project sharing their views, data and patterns. This procedure is by nature very sensitive and to this end it will be conducted in accordance with the national legislation and the transposed EU data protection directives. In the following paragraphs, some key aspects of the different national legislations are presented for each of the pilots as an overview for the pilot demonstration boundary conditions.

3.3.1. Greek pilot site

The Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDPA) is a constitutionally consolidated independent Authority. The Hellenic Data Protection Authority was established with Law 2472/97, which incorporates into the Greek law European Directive 95/46/EC. This Directive sets new rules for the protection of personal data in the member states of the European Union.

The primary goal of the HDPA is the protection of citizens from the unlawful processing of their personal data and their assistance in case it is established that their rights have been violated in any sector.

Law 2472/1997 protects citizens' rights vis-a-vis those who keep and process their personal data (Data Controllers). These rights are the following:

The right to information

The Data Controller must inform you about the collection of your personal data. You have the right to know the identity of the Data Controller, the purpose for which your data is being collected and processed, as well as the identity of anyone to whom your data is disclosed.

The right to access

You have the right to know whether your personal data are being processed or have been processed. More specifically, you have the right to request and obtain from the Controller, without undue delay and in an intelligible and express manner, information about the nature of your personal data, their origin, the purposes of processing and the recipients, if any, thereof.

In order to exercise the right of access you can send a letter (by registered mail) to the Controller. Keep a copy of the letter, the postal receipt and any response you might receive from the Controller.

The right to object

You have the right to object to the processing of your personal data by sending a notice to the Controller requiring them to correct or to delete your personal data.

Data Controllers must respect the provisions of Law 2472/1997 (and 3471/2006 regarding electronic communications) and more specifically:

1. They must collect personal data fairly and lawfully.
2. They must process only the data which are necessary for one or more specified purposes.
3. They must make sure that they keep data accurate and up to date.
4. They must retain data only for as long as is deemed necessary for the purpose of the collection and process thereof.
5. In order to carry out the data processing, the Controller must choose employees with relevant professional qualifications providing sufficient guarantees in terms of technical expertise and personal integrity to ensure such confidentiality.
6. The Controller must implement appropriate organisational and technical measures to secure data and protect them against accidental or unlawful destruction, accidental loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure or access as well as any other form of unlawful processing.
7. If the data processing is carried out on behalf of the Controller, by a person not dependent upon him, the relevant assignment must necessarily be in writing.

8. The Controller must respect the data subject's rights to information, access and objection.
9. They must meet their obligations vis-a-vis the DPA (notification, granting of permit).
10. They must be kept informed on any Decisions, Directives or Recommendations issued by the DPA that may be important to them.

The Greek Pilot Site will be comprised of approximately 60 residences that will participate in the project. This number may be altered based on the final selection of the users and the engagement approaches that will be used. All of the premises that will participate in the ACCEPT Project are located in Aspra Spitia, a prefecture of Viotia in Greece. The Community of Aspra Spitia consists of approximately 1,088 residences, forming a community of more than 3,000 people. Except for the residential buildings, there are educational buildings, buildings accommodating public services such as the Hellenic Coast Guard local team and the National Health System clinic as well as several more public buildings and businesses.

MYTILINEOS, adopting the role of leading the Greek Site in the ACCEPT Project, will soon be testing energy efficiency related schemes in the energy community of Aspra Spitia and offer innovative digital services and access to revenue streams that can financially support its functions and secure its sustainability and effective energy transition.

3.3.2. Dutch pilot site

According to the transposed EU directive on Data Protection, the lead partners of the Dutch pilot site have summarised the privacy declaration principles to be applied in their pilots. The personal data will be handled carefully and confidentially and in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Basic data management principles for the Dutch pilot site:

- ACCEPT only uses personal data for a clearly defined purpose
- ACCEPT only processes the personal data that are necessary for the purpose
- ACCEPT processes personal data in a careful and secure manner
- ACCEPT ensures that the personal data is correct and is adjusted if necessary
- ACCEPT does not store personal data longer than necessary
- ACCEPT takes measures to protect personal data
- ACCEPT describes why they need the user data. Indicatively, ACCEPT needs a user's data in occasions such as the following ones:
 - Invitation to information sessions;
 - Consultation with advisor;
 - When participating in the project;
 - For the project newsletter subscription, etc.

ACCEPT stores data retrieved, for example, when a user fills-in a form on the site, contacts the consortium by telephone or speak to someone from the project.

Indicative types of data stored within the project, which are always made transparent, are presented below:

- name
- Address
- telephone number
- e-mail address

ACCEPT does not store your personal data of Dutch pilot users for longer than is necessary for the purpose of the data processing. Upon termination of the project, all personal data will be destroyed. ACCEPT will only share the Dutch pilot users' information with their consent. At this case, an agreement with the other party takes place so that they also adhere to the same privacy rules as the municipality. ACCEPT remains responsible for the user's privacy. The user's personal data are well protected so that:

- the data is not misused;
- the data are not lost;
- nobody can access the data without permission;
- nobody edits the data without permission to do so, etc.

Each Dutch pilot participant has the right to:

- i. view their data;
- ii. have them adjusted;
- iii. have them removed in some cases;
- iv. transfer them;
- v. restrict of data processing
- vi. object to the data processing.

Vrijstad Energie is the lead contact for the pilot site able to handle and answer questions about the users' data, this privacy statement (the privacy declaration can be found in Annex 2), their rights or about privacy in general. The specific contact person for privacy of Vrijstad Energie is Sandra de Wolff.

3.3.3. Swiss pilot site

Despite the fact that Switzerland is not a member of the EU or EEA, organizations within the country must comply with GDPR regulations to a certain extent. In fact, the GDPR applies to an organization and to the stored data related to European individuals in each of the following cases [7]:

- An organization provides services or goods to individuals in the EU;
- An organization processes or is involved in processing personal data of EU individuals;
- An organization monitors the online behaviour of EU users;
- An organization analyses the activities of EU users when they use the organization's app or browse its website.

The Swiss Federal Act on Data Protection (FADP) of June 19th, 1992, aims to protect the privacy and fundamental rights of individuals when processing their data, as stated in Art.1 of FADP [8]. The act applies to the processing of data of individuals and legal entities by:

- a) private individuals;
- b) federal bodies.

In addition, the main objectives of the FADP are (a) to maintain good data processing practices and (b) to facilitate international data exchange by providing a comparable level of protection [9], which is achieved by regulating cross-border data transfers in cases where there is a need for data protection. A transfer can be prohibited if, for example, the recipient country cannot provide an adequate level of data protection. Both private individuals and government agencies that may be involved in cross-border data transfers are subject to due diligence, and the transfer of data files abroad is subject to notification in case adequate protection is not in place. In the absence of such protection, data may only be

transferred abroad if other safeguards ensure protection, in particular contractual clauses or agreements within the same legal entity.

The national data protection supervisory authority in Switzerland is the Federal Data Protection and Information Commissioner [10], which is appointed by the Federal Council and monitors compliance by federal authorities with the FADP. Specific details on Swiss research innovation regulations, which also include ethical aspects, can be found in [11] (German only).

A fully revised Federal Data Protection Act is currently being drafted and expected to put into force in the second half of 2022 [12]. Until the new FADP comes into force, processing of personal data must comply with new provisions, as documented in [2]. Of relevance, among other main characteristics pointed out in [13], is that the new FADP only protects the privacy of natural persons about whom personal data are processed, while the data of legal entities are no longer included in the new FADP. This brings the scope of application of the new FADP closer to the GDPR. Data protection provisions for legal entities remain covered within Art. 28 of the Swiss Civil Code [14].

The Swiss pilot site is represented by two separate areas with different main characteristics. First, the area of Tesserete consists of a residential neighbourhood with 11 single and multi-family houses, complemented by commercial units such as a public swimming pool, a soccer field building with several offices, and a district heating plant. Second, the Massagno nursing home consists of a 5-story residential building with 30 apartments, a community center, and a commercial kitchen.

AEM, as the project leader for the Swiss pilot site, complies with the applicable Swiss Federal Act on Data Protection (FADP) and, where appropriate, the GDPR provisions regulating data protection of individuals and legal entities participating in the project.

3.3.4. Spanish Pilot site

Besides the already analysed GDPR Directive, another applicable EU Directive that is of interest for the Spanish pilot site is 2002/58/EC on Privacy and Electronic Communications, otherwise known as ePrivacy Directive (ePD). This is an EU directive on data protection and privacy in the digital age. This directive guides the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector. This Directive was amended by Directive 2009/136, which introduces several changes, especially in what concerns cookies. The European Commission adopted the ePrivacy Regulation proposal COM(2017) 10 final 2017/0003(COD). This proposal rules for all electronic communications and includes:

- New players: providers of electronic communication services such as WhatsApp, Facebook and Skype;
- Stronger rules;
- Privacy is guaranteed for Communications content and metadata;
- New business opportunities developed using the data provided by users through a consent request;
- Simpler rules on cookies;
- Protection against spam, etc.

The Spanish Data Protection Agency is the independent Public Authority in charge of the Data Protection and was established with the Organic Law 5/1992 (LORTAD). The Spanish Data Protection Legislation incorporated the European Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). This Directive set new rules for the protection of personal data in the member states of the European Union.

In order to adapt and develop certain matters contained in the European Regulation, the Spanish Parliament has approved the Organic Law 3/2018 of 5 December on the Protection of Personal Data and the Guarantee of Digital Rights. The Law facilitates the exercise of the specific rights conferred to the data subjects by requiring that the means for exercising such rights are easily accessible.

- The right to information

In order to enforce the principle of transparency, the new Law regulates the way in which citizens are informed about the processing of their data and opts for a layered information system. In a first layer, Data subjects shall therefore be informed about the basic aspects of the processing and data collection, namely identity the Data Controller, the purpose of processing and the rights the subjects possess among other basic information. They must be informed also about how to access to more detailed information -through a direct link- contained in a second layer, if they so require.

- The right to access

The new Law recognizes the right of access and, where appropriate, the right to rectify or suppress the data of deceased persons to persons connected with them, unless the deceased had prohibited such access, rectification or deletion.

- Minors consent

With regard to the processing of the personal data of minors, the Law sets the minimum age for autonomous consent at 14 years. Similarly, it regulates the right to be forgotten in relation to data provided by minors to social networks and other information society services. This right may be exercised by the minor her/himself or by third parties while she/he's still a minor.

- Whistleblowing systems

The Law also contains a specific article relating to the processing of personal data within the framework of whistleblowing systems. It allows anonymous dilation from employees to communicate infractions in Data Protection.

- Video surveillance, sound and digital devices

The Law updates the guarantees applicable to citizens in relation to the use of video surveillance devices, geolocation, sound recording and other digital devices in the workplace. The employer can use these devices to control their employees' work nevertheless they must be previously informed and the devices cannot be placed in changing rooms, rest or dining areas. Video and audio surveillance devices can be used in public places but only for security or safety reasons. All non-criminal related data must be deleted in less than a month.

- Processing Personal Data

Controllers must retain data only for as long as is deemed necessary for the purpose of the collection and process thereof (3 months unless specific cases). Controllers must keep it accurate and up to date. Controllers must block Personal Data and avoid any possibility of Data processing and display, once it has been required to be rectified or deleted.

- Digital Rights

The Law specifically includes new "digital rights" such as universal access to internet, secure and appropriate use of Personal Data, and the right for users to rectify and object that applies in digital media and social networks.

The Spanish Pilot Site will be comprised of 50 residences that will participate in the Project, 15 of which will have PV installation on them. The users will be located in Murcia, in southeast Spain and will be selected from members and customers of La Solar energy cooperative. La Solar and MIWenergia with their roles of project leader and technical support, will comply with GDPR requirements in all processes related to user interaction and to collect personal data.

4. Gender Equity Plan

Article 33 of the ACCEPT Grant Agreement incorporate the HORIZON and EC guidelines for gender equality. According to this provision, all project partners must put their best efforts in order to provide equal opportunities of involvement in the project to employs and users regardless of their gender. In this way, the gender dimension is attempted to be introduced in the European research domain following the guidelines of Article 16 of the EU regulation 1291/2013 on “Gender Equality”. The objective is to achieve gender balance in all levels, namely administrative, scientific and managerial.

ACCEPT attempts to introduce gender balance in three main domains applicable within the project as presented in Figure 15. The ways to achieve such a goal are passing through different practices such as the establishment of an equal standards policy, the implementation of countermeasures against gender bias, the promotion of transparency and finally the practical attempt of each partner to distribute the workload of the project to teams with wide gender representation, which are less skewed towards the male employees.

Figure 15 Domains in which ACCEPT attempts to achieve gender balance

ACCEPT consortium comprises multi-cultural teams and ensures the participation of multiple genders which is actually a great advantage as multiple mentalities are combined into a fruitful cooperation. ACCEPT considers research and innovation to be inherently connected to progressiveness and thus the scientific progress will be accompanied with a questioning of genders and social norms both within consortium and in the living labs.

European Institute for Gender Equity (EIGE) had declared that gender aspects are involved in the energy domain with respect to the energy technologies, the energy requirements and usage patterns as well as the perception of technologies. To this end, the overrepresentation of males in such scientific areas adapts the product designs to their needs. The viewpoint of often all-male committees and teams is conceived as “objective” and/or “neutral” while it actually creates a significant, in-built gender bias that

marginalizes the opinion of women or non-binary people. ACCEPT will exploit every opportunity possible to advocate on equal opportunities and equal gender representation raising awareness on the issue. Gender equity is actually one of the pillars of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework that ACCEPT is committed to incorporate in the project.

The ACCEPT Digital ToolBox and overall outcomes refers to all users regardless of their gender and socio-cultural background. The wide gender representation and the equal opportunities provided by ACCEPT will be monitored for each partner and for each pilot. The main KPIs monitored comprise the percentage of each gender (%) in the project teams of each partner and in the living labs of each pilot. Other gender aspects will be identified and their fulfillment will be quantified through the project lifetime.

5. Conclusions

Due respect to the ethical aspects of research and compliance with national, regional and EU legislation and ethics directives are of utmost importance for ACCEPT project. Ethics-related issues are divided into two (2) categories:

- *processes and requirements that are utilized for participant recruitment in the research framework*

Humans (H)

- *procedures of information Collection – Storage – Protection – Retrieval - Destruction and verification of compliance with application data regulation*

Protection of Personal Data (POPD)

After the specification of the technical criteria that are essential for the pilot users in order to be part of ACCEPT research activities, specific requirements, processes and structures need to be created and applied in order to ensure that the user personal information will be treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Addressing the **right to information**, the pilot site partner should analyse in detail the research concept of ACCEPT to the stakeholders involved in each pilot together with the expectations from their participation. Furthermore, a written and signed consent form is essential in order to confirm voluntary participation and acknowledgement of the pilot activity involvement requirements. **Data minimisation policy** should be applied preventing from collection of information that is not essential together with extra attention to avoid accidental exposure of personal data through “**data shadows**”. Upon data collection, the data will be **anonymised/ pseudonymised** as a first processing step and then they will be stored with all the proper **encryption** in order to guarantee safe access. An elaborate user management will grant access only to specific, qualified personnel through the appropriate **authentication & authorisation** processes. Finally, the “right to be forgotten” will be guaranteed and its participant will maintain their **option to withdraw** from the project at any time.

ACCEPT has a robust **gender equity plan** at the project team and living lab level that will be gradually enriched through the course of the project and will be monitored on a regular basis.

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Annex 1

- ***E.U. legislation for General Data Protection Regulation- EU 2016/679***

Data Collection, Storage, Processing and data protection

In April 2016 the GDPR (2016/679) was finally approved by the EU Parliament. The regulation refers to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data enforcement date: 25 May 2018 - at which time those organizations in non-compliance will face heavy fines.

It replaces the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC. The GDPR harmonizes data privacy laws across Europe, protects and empowers all EU citizens' data privacy and reshapes the way organizations across the region approach data privacy.

Towards defining the detailed procedure for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction in the project the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - is described below. The GDPR applies generally to processing the personal data of data subjects residing in the Union, regardless of the company's location. It also applies to the processing of personal data by controllers and processors in the EU, regardless of whether the processing takes place in the EU or not. Very important: the GDPR strengthens Data Subjects rights and imposes strong penalties on breaches, dealing with personal data.

The GDPR introduces newly:

- Right to be Forgotten (Article 17)

The "right to be forgotten" entitles the data subject to have the data controller erase his/her personal data, cease further dissemination of the data, and potentially have third parties halt processing of the data. The conditions for erasure, as outlined in article 17 of GDPR, include the data no longer being relevant to original purposes for processing, or a data subjects withdrawing consent.

- Right to data portability (Article 20)

GDPR introduces data portability - the right for a data subject to receive the personal data concerning them, which they have previously provided in a 'commonly use and machine-readable format' and have the right to transmit that data to another controller.

- Privacy by Design (Article 23)

Privacy by design is part of a legal requirement with the GDPR. At its core, privacy by design calls for the inclusion of data protection from the onset of the designing of systems, rather than an addition. Article 23 calls for controllers to hold and process only the data necessary for the completion of its duties (data minimization), as well as limiting the access to personal data to those needing to act out the processing.

- Penalties (Chapter 8)

Under GDPR, organizations in breach of GDPR can be fined up to 4% of annual global turnover or €20 Million (whichever is greater). This is the maximum fine that can be imposed for the most serious infringements e.g. not having sufficient customer consent to process data or violating the core of Privacy by Design concepts. There is a tiered approach to fines e.g. a company can be fined 2% for not having their records in order (article 28), not notifying the supervising authority and data subject about a breach or not conducting impact assessment. It is important to note that these rules apply to both controllers and processors -- meaning 'clouds' will not be exempt from GDPR enforcement.

- Data Protection Officers

Currently, controllers are required to notify their data processing activities with local DPAs. Under GDPR it will not be necessary to submit notifications / registrations to each local DPA of data processing

activities, nor will it be a requirement to notify / obtain approval for transfers based on the Model Contract Clauses (MCCs). Instead, there will be internal record keeping requirements, as further explained below, and DPO appointment will be mandatory only for those controllers and processors whose core activities consist of processing operations which require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale or of special categories of data or data relating to criminal convictions and offences. Importantly, the DPO:

- *Must be appointed on the basis of professional qualities and, in particular, expert knowledge on data protection law and practices*
- *May be a staff member or an external service provider*
- *Contact details must be provided to the relevant DPA*
- *Must be provided with appropriate resources to carry out their tasks and maintain their expert knowledge*
- *Must report directly to the highest level of management*
- *Must not carry out any other tasks that could result in a conflict of interest.*

The GDPR differentiates between roles: data processor and data controller (Chapter IV).

A controller is the entity that determines the purposes, conditions and means of the processing of personal data, while the processor is an entity, which processes personal data on behalf of the controller. Essential legal principles of privacy in the GDPR are:

- Data Sovereignty

Data sovereignty is the concept that information which has been converted and stored in binary digital form is subject to the laws of the country in which it is located.

- Self Determination

The individual decides on the disclosure and use of his personal data (that explicitly covers the collection, storage, process and disclosure of personal data).

- Autonomy – (the way of handling personal data within the rights granted)

Enabling individuals to extent their privacy and protect them against interferences.

Main aspects of these principles are:

1. Subject of data sovereignty: Personal Data
2. Being holder of rights
 - a. Clear and specific right to inform – before, during and after the data process
 - b. Consent requirement
 - c. Right to correction
 - d. Right to erase
 - e. Right to restrict data process
 - f. Right to appeal – Not being object of pure automatic data process that have legal effect
3. Data controller and processor as holder of obligations
 - g. Fulfilling principles of data processing
 - h. Obligation to inform in intelligible and easy language, transparently with the key facts presented
4. Principles of data processing (Art. 5 GDPR)
 - i. Lawful, fairly and transparent data process

Personal data in GDPR:

According to Art. 4 I GDPR any information related to a natural person or 'Data Subject' that can be used to directly or indirectly identify the person. It can be anything from a name, a photo, an email address, bank details, and posts on social networking websites, medical information, or a computer IP address.

Important is the relative meaning of personal data in context of the term identifiable. Art.4 sec. 1 GDPR differs between information referring directly and indirectly to an identifiable person. Relevant are two

categories of data: Personal data and non-personal data. As the first term has already been mentioned, the second category can be divided into two further kind of data:

Anonymous data: Anonymous data are information that do not contain any information about a natural person. The person-related information has been cleared from the datasets. Such data do not fall under the scope of the GDPR and are not relevant in the legal assessment.

Pseudonymous data: Pseudonymization of personal information is a procedure where person-related information is replaced by non-identifiers in order to ensure that these informational cannot be assigned to natural persons anymore.

GDPR Principles relating to processing of personal data are (Article 5):

Lawful, fairly and transparent data process

The data process is bound to the data protection principles, which represent the fundament on which the data process is executed. The data protection principles can be found in Art. 5 GDPR.

Data minimization

According to Art. 5 GDPR, data minimization requires that data are only processed due to a legitimate purpose at the time of collection. The data process shall be restricted to the minimum amount necessary to fulfil the pursuit purpose of the data process. According to this definition, the data process has to be appropriate, substantial and restricted to the minimum amount necessary.

Purpose limitation principle

Processing personal data is only allowed with prove of a particular, explicitly determined and lawful purpose and not for any other purposes afterwards.

Compatible further processing

Nevertheless, it is not excluded to process data on the base of different purposes. For processing personal data, it is recommended to gain the respective consent. Besides, according to Article 6 IV GDPR, processing data for a purpose other than the original purpose requires to be compatible, and vice versa not incompatible, with the original purpose. With regard to the wording of Art. 6 IV GRPD, "further processing" implies that subject is the extension of the current data process and not a new data process independent of the previous data processes. A new data process requires a new legal basis, whereas the extension of the current data process does not require a new legal basis, but a reasonable justification according to Art. 6 IV GDPR. Decisive criterion is compatibility. Insofar, the further processing of data is not restricted to the pure compatibility, but the decisive criterion whether data process derives from the original purpose.

Accuracy

Accuracy according to Art. 5 sec. GDPR means that personal data have to be objectively correct and if necessary, to be updated. Thereby objectively correct means that all information about a person have to match with reality.

Restriction of storing data

In order to avoid long-term storing, personal data have to collected and stored as long as it is necessary for the respective purpose. This constitutes a time limit for storing personal data. Whenever the purpose is reached, all personal data have to be erased from the data storage.

Integrity and Confidentiality

The data controller has to guarantee the safety and security of personal data during the data process. Thereby, he is fully responsible and so, according to this principle, obligated to implement suitable technical and organizational measures in order to prevent unintentional harm of personal data.

Lawful data processing

The GDPR strengthens the conditions for consent, as the request for consent must be given in an intelligible and easily accessible form, with the purpose for data processing attached to that consent. Consent must be clear and distinguishable from other matters and provided in an intelligible and easily

accessible form, using clear and plain language. It must be as easy to withdraw consent as it is to give it.

Further information can be found at the European Commission Webpage (<https://www.eugdpr.org/>). While the new legislation will be standard all around Europe, a reference to the current local legislations is provided.

Annex 2¹

Privacyverklaring

We gaan zorgvuldig en vertrouwelijk met uw persoonsgegevens om. Hoe het project ACCEPT dit doet is vastgelegd in de Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG).

ACCEPT:

- gebruikt persoonsgegevens alleen voor een duidelijk omschreven doel
- verwerkt alleen de persoonsgegevens die voor het doel noodzakelijk zijn
- verwerkt persoonsgegevens op een zorgvuldige en veilige manier
- zorgt er voor dat de persoonsgegevens juist zijn en zo nodig worden aangepast
- bewaart persoonsgegevens niet langer dan noodzakelijk
- treft maatregelen om persoonsgegevens te beschermen
- beschrijft waarom we uw gegevens nodig hebben
- als u meedoet met het project heeft ACCEPT uw gegevens nodig. Bijvoorbeeld voor:
 - Uitnodigen informatieavonden
 - Gesprek met adviseur
 - Bij deelname in het project
 - Indien onze nieuwsbrief wil ontvangen

ACCEPT slaat deze gegevens op. Dit gebeurt o.a. als u een formulier op de site invult, telefonisch contact opneemt of iemand van het project spreekt.

Persoonsgegevens

Het project slaat verschillende gegevens op. De precieze gegevens zijn nog niet bekend maar worden altijd transparant gemaakt alvorens ze verwerkt worden

In ieder geval:

- naam adres
- telefoonnummer
- e-mailadres

Hoelang we uw gegevens bewaren

ACCEPT bewaart uw persoonsgegevens niet langer dan noodzakelijk is voor het doel van de gegevensverwerking. Bij beëindiging van het project worden alle persoonsgegevens vernietigd.

Delen met anderen

ACCEPT deelt uw gegevens alleen uw toestemming. We sluiten dan een overeenkomst met de andere partij af zodat ook zij zich aan dezelfde privacyregels als de gemeente houden. ACCEPT blijft dan wel verantwoordelijk voor uw privacy.

Beveiliging

¹ Privacy declaration informing ACCEPT participant's in the Dutch pilot of how their personal data will be handled within the project and in alignment with the GDPR.

Uw persoonsgegevens worden goed beschermd zodat:

- geen misbruik van uw gegevens wordt gemaakt
- uw gegevens niet verloren gaan
- niemand zonder toestemming bij uw gegevens kan
- niemand zonder toestemming uw gegevens bewerkt

Uw rechten

U heeft het recht:

- uw gegevens in te zien
- ze aan te laten passen
- ze in een aantal gevallen te laten verwijderen
- ze over te dragen
- op beperking van de gegevensverwerking
- bezwaar te maken tegen de gegevensverwerking

Neem hiervoor contact op met Vrijstad Energie.

Contactgegevens

Voor vragen over uw gegevens, deze privacyverklaring, uw rechten of over privacy in het algemeen neemt u contact op met:

Sandra de Wolff mail sandra@vrijstadenergie.nl
Aanspreekpunt privacy van Vrijstad Energie